

THE EFFECT OF STRAIN GAGE SIZE ON MEASUREMENT ERRORS IN TEXTILE COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Eric J. Lang¹ and Tsu-Wei Chou²

¹ *The Why Not Corp., 743 W. Sparrow Rd., Springfield, OH 45502, USA*

² *Center for Composite Materials, and Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Delaware, Newark, DE 19716 USA*

SUMMARY: The heterogeneous nature of textile composites on the microstructural scale leads to variation in the local strain field within the unit cell. This variation can result in inaccurate measurement of the average global strain when using strain gages of insufficient size. A statistical model for sensor error is presented which leads to expressions for sensor variance. The model includes the effects of unit cell size, gage length, gage width, microstructural defects and irregularities, and instrument error. The proposed model is verified experimentally using a plain woven graphite-epoxy composite material and strain gages of various lengths. The experimental results are compared with analytical predictions. A set of guidelines for the use of strain gages on textile composites has been developed.

KEYWORDS: textile composites, statistics, microstructure mechanical properties, strain gage

INTRODUCTION

Consider the problem of determining the average macroscopic strains on the surface of a heterogeneous material using a relatively compact strain gage. This problem arises, for instance, when determining the bulk material properties of a textile composite material by mechanical testing.

The area of the strain gage is smaller than the macroscopic area and therefore, if the strain distribution is not constant, the sensor output and the macroscopic strain may not be in agreement. The gage averages the strain over the gage section. If the gage is located in a region of below average strain, the sensor output will be lower than the average macroscopic strain. Conversely, if the gage is located in a region of above average strain, the sensor output will be higher than the average macroscopic strain. In general, it is not known whether a strain gage is in a region of above average strain, average strain, or below average strain. Thus, the sensor output tends to be a random variable with some probability distribution around the true macroscopic strain. Ideally, this probability distribution is closely centered around the actual macroscopic strain value. In practice, the distribution depends on factors such as gage size and unit cell size.

A non-uniform strain distribution may be caused by random defects or material irregularities introduced during manufacturing. Alternatively, the heterogeneous microstructure of the

material can cause variation in the local strain field. This microstructurally induced strain variation has been predicted analytically and measured experimentally using Moiré Interferometry methods[1]. The magnitude of the strain variation is predicted to be a function of the relative stiffnesses of the fiber and matrix material as well as the fiber architecture. The greater the difference in stiffness, the larger the strain variation.

Moiré interferometry also shows distinct variation in the strain field due to the microstructure in various textile composite materials. While these variations may not be significant if the tows are relatively small in comparison to the gage size, when the tows are large, the variation is likely to lead to measurement errors. Some textile composite materials such as through-the-thickness, multi-layer weaves and 3-dimensional braids [2-4] have quite large unit cells -- in some cases exceeding one or more inches.

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the effect strain gage size has on the accuracy of strain measurements made on periodically heterogeneous materials. A statistical model for sensor output including the effects of unit cell size, strain variation within the unit cell, gage length, gage width, material defects and irregularities, and instrument error is proposed. The model is verified experimentally using a plain weave graphite-polyester composite. The details of the theoretical analysis and experimental verification can be found in Refs. [5, 6].

DEFINITIONS AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

Let us decompose the strain $\varepsilon_{ij}(x,y)$ at a point on the surface of a heterogeneous material with a periodically repeated microstructure or unit cell into a constant component $\bar{\varepsilon}_{ij}$ which represents the macroscopic average strain, a random component $\varepsilon_{ij}^d(x,y)$ which represents the effects of material defects and irregularities, and a periodic component $\varepsilon_{ij}^u(x,y)$ which represents the local strain variation within the unit cell caused by the textile microstructure. The actual strain at a point is the sum of these three components, or

$$\varepsilon_{ij}(x,y) = \bar{\varepsilon}_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij}^d(x,y) + \varepsilon_{ij}^u(x,y) \quad (1)$$

with

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{ij} \equiv \frac{1}{A} \iint_A \varepsilon_{ij}(x,y) dA \quad E[\varepsilon_{ij}^d(x,y)] \equiv 0 \quad \iint_{A_u} \varepsilon_{ij}^u(x,y) dA \equiv 0 \quad (2)$$

where A is some macroscopic area, $E[]$ denotes the statistical expectation[7], and A_u is the area of a unit cell.

Each component of the unit cell strain is, in general, a function of all the components of global average strain as well as position within the unit cell. Assuming linear elasticity, the effects on the unit cell strain of each component of macroscopic strain can be superposed. The unit cell strains are related to the global average strains by an equation of the form

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^u(x,y) = F_{ijkl}(x,y) \bar{\varepsilon}_{kl} \quad (3)$$

Symmetry of the strain tensor requires,

$$F_{ijkl} = F_{jikl} = F_{ijlk} \quad (4)$$

which reduces the maximum number of independent constants in F_{ijkl} to thirty-six. It should be remembered that the components of F_{ijkl} are functions of position in the unit cell and have periodicity conditions. For simplicity, we will consider the case of rectangular unit cells in which F_{ijkl} and $\varepsilon_{ij}^u(x,y)$ must satisfy the following periodicity conditions

$$F_{ijkl}(x^* + m\lambda_x, y^* + n\lambda_y) = F_{ijkl}(x^*, y^*) \quad \begin{cases} m = 1, 2, \dots \\ n = 1, 2, \dots \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^u(x^* + m\lambda_x, y^* + n\lambda_y) = \varepsilon_{ij}^u(x^*, y^*) \quad \begin{cases} m = 1, 2, \dots \\ n = 1, 2, \dots \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where λ_x and λ_y are the lengths of the unit cell in the x and y directions and (x^*, y^*) is any point in the unit cell. Similar periodicity conditions can be derived for unit cells of different shapes.

Strain gages are usually placed on the surface of a material where there are only three non-zero strains. Thus, in practical situations, the nontrivial components of Eqn 3 can be represented by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx}^u \\ \varepsilon_{yy}^u \\ \varepsilon_{xy}^u \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{11} & f_{12} & f_{13} \\ f_{21} & f_{22} & f_{23} \\ f_{31} & f_{32} & f_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx} \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_{yy} \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{or} \quad \{\varepsilon^u\} = [F]\{\bar{\varepsilon}\} \quad (7)$$

Similarly, the strain at a point due to material defects is given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx}^d \\ \varepsilon_{yy}^d \\ \varepsilon_{xy}^d \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{\varepsilon}_{xx} \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_{yy} \\ \bar{\varepsilon}_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{or} \quad \{\varepsilon^d\} = [G]\{\bar{\varepsilon}\} \quad (8)$$

In the previous equations, we use an upper case letter to denote a matrix and a lower case letter to denote the elements of the matrix. The tensor F_{ijkl} should not be confused with the matrix F .

The components of G are assumed to be random variables, independent of each other and independent from one point to the next in space. The expected value for each component is zero, and, for the purposes of this analysis, the variance is assumed to be the same for all components and all positions in the unit cell. We will denote this variance by σ_δ^2 and it is defined by,

$$\sigma_\delta^2 \equiv E \left[\frac{1}{A} \iint_A g_{ij}^2(x,y) dA \right] \quad (9)$$

SENSOR OUTPUT EQUATIONS

On the surface of a material, there is the possibility of three independent strain components. However, a strain gage gives only one measurement output. Most gages are designed to have very low sensitivities to transverse and shearing strains and the contribution of these strains to the gage output is neglected in the following analysis. The output of the sensor depends on

the orientation of the sensor relative to the global coordinates, and the strain in the global coordinates.

Figure 1 shows the coordinate system used to describe the position and orientation of the strain gage. Primes are used to denote the gage coordinates. The lower left-hand corner of the gage is located at a position (X,Y) and the sensing direction of the gage is rotated in the counter-clockwise direction to an angle ϕ relative to the global coordinate system x-y.

Following Eqn 1, the strain in the direction of the strain gage is

$$\varepsilon_g(x, y, \phi) = \bar{\varepsilon}_g + \varepsilon_g^d(x, y, \phi) + \varepsilon_g^u(x, y, \phi) \quad (10)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\varepsilon}_g &= \cos^2(\phi)\bar{\varepsilon}_{xx} + \sin^2(\phi)\bar{\varepsilon}_{yy} + 2\cos(\phi)\sin(\phi)\bar{\varepsilon}_{xy} \\ \varepsilon_g^d(x, y, \phi) &= \cos^2(\phi)\varepsilon_{xx}^d(x, y) + \sin^2(\phi)\varepsilon_{yy}^d(x, y) + 2\cos(\phi)\sin(\phi)\varepsilon_{xy}^d(x, y) \\ \varepsilon_g^u(x, y, \phi) &= \cos^2(\phi)\varepsilon_{xx}^u(x, y) + \sin^2(\phi)\varepsilon_{yy}^u(x, y) + 2\cos(\phi)\sin(\phi)\varepsilon_{xy}^u(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Foil strain gages currently in common usage consist of a single thin strip of metal which traverses back and forth across the gage area. In this analysis, we will treat the strain gages as areal sensors. Areal sensor measure the average strain over an area. With this assumption, the results of the present analysis can also apply to strain gages made from piezoelectric materials.[8]

In most cases a strain gage is positioned without any knowledge of its location relative to the underlying unit cell. Therefore, the variables X and Y shown in Fig. 1 are assumed to be uniformly distributed random variables with the following probability density functions:

$$f_X(X) = \begin{cases} 0 & X < 0 \\ 1/\lambda_x & 0 \leq X \leq \lambda_x \\ 0 & \lambda_x < X \end{cases} \quad f_Y(Y) = \begin{cases} 0 & Y < 0 \\ 1/\lambda_y & 0 \leq Y \leq \lambda_y \\ 0 & \lambda_y < Y \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 1: Coordinate system detailing the position of the strain gage

The strain at a point (x,y) can be written as a function of (x', y', X, Y) by making the substitution

$$\begin{Bmatrix} x \\ y \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\phi) & -\sin(\phi) \\ \sin(\phi) & \cos(\phi) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} x' \\ y' \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} X \\ Y \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Using this change of variables and the assumption of an areal sensor, the measured strain, ϵ_m , is given by

$$\epsilon_m(X, Y, \phi) = \bar{\epsilon}_m + \epsilon_m^d(X, Y, \phi) + \epsilon_m^u(X, Y, \phi) \quad (14)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\epsilon}_m &= \bar{\epsilon}_g \\ \epsilon_m^d(X, Y, \phi) &= \frac{1}{A_g} \int_{L_y} \int_{L_x} \epsilon_g^d(x', y', X, Y, \phi) dx' dy' \\ \epsilon_m^u(X, Y, \phi) &= \frac{1}{A_g} \int_{L_y} \int_{L_x} \epsilon_g^u(x', y', X, Y, \phi) dx' dy' \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where A_g is the area of the gage.

Let us define the apparent strain, which is the strain actually recorded by the data acquisition system, as

$$\epsilon_a \equiv \epsilon_m + \epsilon_I \quad (16)$$

where ϵ_m is the actual average strain on the gage section, and ϵ_I is the random error introduced by all other sources such as gage defects, instrument errors (calibration, gain, gage factor, etc.), and interference. To detect the error components we must analyze the variation in gage output. Since the errors are statistically independent, the variance in the apparent strain is the sum of three variances :

$$\sigma_a^2 = \sigma_u^2 + \sigma_d^2 + \bar{\epsilon}_g^2 \sigma_I^2 \quad (17)$$

where σ_a^2 is the apparent or measured sensor output variance, σ_u^2 is the variance due to the microstructure, σ_d^2 is the variance due to the material defects, and $\bar{\epsilon}_g^2 \sigma_I^2$ is the variance due to instrument error.

A SPECIFIC EXAMPLE

In this section some assumptions are made about the relationship between unit cell strain and macroscopic strain which allow us to find closed form expressions for σ_u^2 . We will consider a balanced plain weave material. The width, spacing, and density of the yarns are the same in both the warp and weft directions. The only geometric parameter important in this study is the microstructure wave length λ , which is the distance it takes for the microstructure to repeat itself in either the warp or weft direction.

In order to find the contribution of unit cell strain to the overall variance, it is necessary to specify the probability distributions of X and Y. Here, we consider the case of random position of a gage on the unit cell for $\phi = 0$. Using the definitions,

$$\alpha \equiv \frac{L_x}{\lambda} \quad \beta \equiv \frac{L_y}{\lambda} \quad \gamma \equiv \frac{\kappa}{\pi\lambda} \quad (18)$$

the variance is given by

$$\sigma_u^2 = \frac{1}{A_g^2} I_2 = \frac{\gamma^2}{\alpha^2 \beta^2} \sin^2(\pi\alpha) \sin^2(\pi\beta) \bar{\epsilon}_{xx}^2 \quad (19)$$

where κ is a parameter which defines the magnitude of the displacement perturbations caused by the microstructure for a given material

Figure 2 shows $\sigma_u/\bar{\epsilon}_g$ as a function of α and β with $\gamma \equiv 1$. It is clear that $\sigma_u/\bar{\epsilon}_g$ generally decreases as the sensor gets longer or wider. Also, if the sensor length or width is a integer multiple of the unit cell length $\sigma_u/\bar{\epsilon}_g$ is zero. In fact, the error is almost zero whenever the gage is wider and longer than the unit cell. Conversely, gages smaller than the unit cell can have large errors.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

In order to validate the theory developed in the previous sections, a series of experiments was performed. Coupons with multiple strain gages were tested in uniaxial tension. The variance in gage output was calculated for each coupon. These observed variances are used to determine which components of the sensor error model are significant.

A graphite-polyester composite material was chosen for the test material in order to maximize the ratio of the stiffness of the reinforcement to the stiffness of the matrix, thereby maximizing the magnitude of the microstructurally induced strain perturbations. A plain

Fig. 2 σ_u/ϵ_g vs function of gage dimensions α and β

weave was the textile form chosen since it has the smallest unit cell size for a given yarn size and thereby minimizes the maximum required gage size. The chosen preform material had 8 warp yarns per 25.4 mm (1") and 8 weft yarns per 25.4 mm (1") giving it microstructure repeat period, λ , of 6.35 mm (0.25"). A four layer laminate was made.

After cure, the material was end-tabbed and cut into 25.4 mm (1") wide and 508 mm (20") long coupons using a diamond tipped blade on a polishing table. This technique allowed accurate parallel cuts to be made. The multiple strain gages were mounted on both sides of eight coupons. The largest gage had a gage length of 12.7 mm (0.5") and an overall length of 20.3 mm (0.8"). Therefore, the gages were placed 25.4 mm (1") apart nominally. The set of gages was centered in the gage section of the coupon. However, in order to properly randomize the test, a random offset in the range of 0.00-6.35 mm (0.00-0.25") was added to the 25.4 mm (1") nominal starting position of the gages. After the random off-sets were generated, the clearance gap between adjacent gages was checked to make sure that two adjacent gages would not overlap. Chance would have it that none of the gages overlapped. Thus, the starting position of each gage was at a randomly assigned position along the tow.

All coupons except Coupon 6 had 7 gages on each side. On one side (6A) of Coupon 6, ten gap-centered gages were mounted while on the other side (6B), ten tow-centered gages were mounted. The nominal length and width of gages for Coupon 6B are 1.575 mm (0.062") and 3.048 mm (0.120"), respectively.

The coupons were loaded to a nominal 0.15 percent strain and the output of each gage was recorded. A plot of gage reading versus average gage reading for Coupon 6B are shown in Fig. 3. Notice how widely dispersed the readings are for Coupon 6B, which has small tow-centered gages, and thus microstructurally induced variation. The results dramatically demonstrate the importance of considering gage size relative to unit cell size.

Fig. 3: Gage output vs average - Coupon 6B

CONCLUSIONS

The variation in strain caused by the microstructure of a textile composite can have a significant effect on the output of strain gages. If gages of the proper size are used, the effect of microstructurally induced variation is essentially eliminated. However, if the gages are too small the measurements can be inaccurate. In fact, with very small gages and composites made of a polymer matrix and a textile preform consisting of a high modulus fiber such as graphite, the magnitude of the error is so large that the measurements are almost worthless. Thus, even though strain gages are usually idealized as "point sensors", their distributed nature can play an important role with regard to their accuracy. A set of guidelines for the use of strain gages on textile materials has been presented in Refs. [5, 6].

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